

AI-PRISM

D4.3 – AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient (III)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101058589. This document reflects only the author's view and the EU Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project Title	AI-Powered human-centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing
Project Acronym	AI-PRISM
Grant Agreement No	101058589
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-01
Start Date of Project	October 1, 2022
Duration of Project	36 months

Name of the deliverable	AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient (III)
Number of the deliverable	D4.3
Related WP number and name	WP4
Related task number and name	T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, T4.4, T4.5
Deliverable dissemination level	PU
Deliverable due date	31.03.2025
Deliverable submission date	31.03.2025
Task leader/Main author	PIAP
Contributing partners	UPV, FBK, KUL
Reviewer(s)	PIAP, UPV

Keywords

Software, versions, Gitlab, AI, CI/CD

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	03.03.2025	Base version	PIAP, UPV, FBK, KUL, SIL, WINGS, TEK, ETRI
v0.2	20.03.2025	First review	PIAP, UPV
v0.3	31.03.2025	Second review	PIAP, UPV

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
WP	Work Package
T	Task
AI	Artificial intelligence
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development/Deployment
TDB	To Be Determined
2D/3D/6D	Two/three/six Dimensions

Contents

1. Introduction	7
1.1. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY	7
1.2. STATUS GUIDELINES	8
2. Architecture of AI-enhancing tools	8
3. Modules	9
3.1. CI/CD FRAMEWORK FOR AI-BASED SOLUTIONS – CD (PIAP)	9
3.1.1. GITLAB TOOLING	9
3.1.2. FRONTEND TEMPLATE	10
3.1.3. CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS	11
3.1.4. MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES	12
3.1.5. ROS OVERLAY WORKSPACE HELM JOB TEMPLATE	12
3.2. AI-BASED PERCEPTION ENHANCING MODULES – PE (FBK)	13
3.2.1. OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION (2D/3D).....	13
3.2.2. OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION	14
3.2.3. PCB GRASPING POINT ESTIMATION	15
3.2.4. PCB POSE ESTIMATION	16
3.2.5. 2D DEFECT DETECTION	17
3.2.6. SPEECH RECOGNITION	18
3.2.7. NLP INTENT AND SLOT	19
3.2.8. PERSON FOLLOWER.....	19
3.2.9. HOOD DETECTION AND TRACKING	20
3.2.10. FOLLOW ME AMR MODULE-UWB.....	21
3.2.11. Inference Component: AI-Engine	21
3.2.12. AFFECTIVE WORKER CONDITION MONITORING	22
3.2.13. HUMAN STATUS ESTIMATION	22
3.2.14. HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION	23
3.3. AI-BASED AGENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – DR (KUL) 24	
3.3.1. COORDINATION OF AGENTS	24

3.3.2.	BT ORCHESTRATOR	25	
3.3.3.	FORCE-BASED BEHAVIOURS	26	
3.3.4.	DEPLOYABLE CONSTRAINT BASED REACTIVE CONTROL.....	27	
3.4.	AI-BASED AMBIENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – CR (UPV)		29
3.4.1.	REASONING MODEL.....	29	
3.4.2.	HRC PAINTING RE/SCHEDULER.....	30	
3.5.	HUMAN - MACHINE INTERACTION (HMI) MODULES – HI (KUL).....	31	
3.5.1.	KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE.....	31	
3.5.2.	HRC ASSEMBLY CONSTRAINT-BASED TASKS	32	
3.5.3.	SPEECH SYNTHESIS	33	
3.5.4.	VOICE CONTROL	33	
3.5.5.	SMART PICK AND PLACE FOR RECYCLING	34	
3.5.6.	COLLABORATIVE ORDER FORMING	35	
3.5.7.	SMART DEPALLETIZING	36	
3.5.8.	AI ASSISTANT.....	36	
3.6.	PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT – PD (KUL)	37	
3.6.1.	PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION TOOLKIT	37	
3.6.2.	PAINTING PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION.....	38	
3.6.3.	MULTIMODAL INTERFACES	39	
3.6.4.	SKILLS FOR COMPLEX TASKS	40	
4.	Conclusions.....	41	
4.1.1.	SUMMARY.....	41	
4.1.2.	NEXT STEPS.....	42	

1. Introduction

1.1. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

This Deliverable describes consecutive releases of the CI/CD framework (code repositories, CI/CD pipelines and project scaffolds to support the development, integration, and validation of AI-based modules), software releases of libraries of AI-based modules to enhance perception and reasoning capabilities of agents in the collaborative ambient, as well as to enable ambient level coordination and learning tasks by human demonstration.

The main objective of WP4 is to enhance the perception and reasoning capabilities of robotic agents using AI based modules. This work package also provides continuous integration / continuous development (CI/CD) pipelines and infrastructure to support development, integration, and validation of AI based solutions in AI-PRISM. The following specific objectives are targeted in WP4:

- Design and validation of continuous integration and validation pipelines for AI-PRISM AI-based solutions.
- Design and development of AI-based perception modules to enhance perception capabilities in the ambient.
- Design and development of AI-based reasoning modules to enhance the reasoning capabilities of individual agents in the collaborative ambient.
- Design and development of AI-based reasoning modules to coordinate activities of groups of agents in the collaborative ambient.
- Develop programming by demonstration methods to transfer knowledge from humans to robots.

It is important to note that the list of components hereby presented corresponds to the status of the components developed in WP4 at the reporting month M30. The companion deliverable D3.3 describes the components developed in WP3 at the same reporting month. The documentation of the latest version of AI-PRISM components is maintained online in <https://documentation.aiprism-srv.cigip.upv.es/guides/>.

1.2. STATUS GUIDELINES

Status	Description
Planned	Task defined and assigned to an Epic
In progress	Task under current development
Ready to test	Task developed and ready to be tested
Completed	Task finished and tested
On hold	Task temporary paused

2. Architecture of AI-enhancing tools

This deliverable completes the definition of the components of AI-PRISM started in D3.3. More specifically, all modules below are developed as part of WP4 – AI enhancing tools. D3.3 provides a high-level overview of the architecture and role of the different components of the AI-PRISM collaborative robotic platform. Additionally, the online documentation and internal documentation of the project describe the Reference Architecture ¹ of AI-PRISM.

WP4 components encompass the AI-enhancing components designed to improve the perception and reasoning capabilities of collaborative robots. To this end, the CI/CD Framework for AI-Based solutions provides online services, project templates and runtime components to facilitate the development and integration of components, as well as the deployment of these components into the ROS-2 based robotic platform developed in WP3.

This deliverable also details the AI-based perception enhancing modules that process input sensor data to perform crucial tasks in collaborative robotics applications such as object and defect detection, pose estimation, speech recognition, or person tracking. These tasks are in last instance used by AI-based reasoning enhancing modules to improve the control and coordination of robotic agents. Finally, this deliverable also includes the released components for Programming by Demonstration (PbD).

¹ <https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/reference-architecture.git>

3. Modules

3.1. CI/CD FRAMEWORK FOR AI-BASED SOLUTIONS – CD (PIAP)

The GitLab software repository is available here: <https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4>

3.1.1. GITLAB TOOLING

Module name		GITLAB TOOLING		
General description		Gitlab tooling is the basis for our CI/CD. The infrastructure is located on independent servers at PIAP. It enables, among others: tracking tasks in the project, code repository, CI/CD pipelines and package and containers registry.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the epic of the second version of the tooling. It includes issue tracking and container registry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduced issue tracking • First CI pipeline integration (frontend_template project) • Added default CI/CD runner • Enabled container registry • Gitlab updates • Extended storage space (>1TB) 	Completed
3.0	April 2025	Third tooling version. It includes more templating features and new component.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reorganization of folders structure • Add Helm-charts to catalogue via CI/CD • Generate helm templates for each component 	In progress

3.1.2. FRONTEND TEMPLATE

Module name		FRONTEND TEMPLATE		
General description		Frontend template based on the project identity colours and theme with examples pages including useful components for the rest of project partners. It also provides general guidelines on how to use it and best practices.		
Gitlab link		NextJS frontend template available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/aiprism_frontend_template		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional frontend template for the project with NextJS framework. It includes the project colours and some basic components in different pages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First NextJS version with generic components • Integration of project theme and styles • First Dockerfile 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	This is the epic of the second version of the template. It includes an update of the look and feel of the template to bring it closer to the theme of the project, including specific components that partners will need. A first integration with Keycloak will be made for the login and jinja templating features will be added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New components added. • Bring the template closer to the theme of the project. • First integration with Keycloak login (different branch). • Continuous integration added. • Minor bugs fixed. • Jinja templating features delayed to next epic. 	Partially completed. ON-HOLD: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keycloak integration Delayed to next epic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating ON-HOLD
3.0	March 31 st 2024	Third frontend version. It includes Jinja templating features and new status component.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating features delayed from the previous epic. 	Partially completed. IN PROCESS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status management component. • Graph component. • Solved issues raised from partners. 	
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3.1.3. CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS

Module name		CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS		
General description		The Cluster Management provides an optimized environment for deploying and managing containerized applications and Kubernetes. It automates the installation of Docker, a single-node cluster with K3s, Helm, and Rancher, simplifying cluster orchestration and management. This toolkit serves as a foundational platform for developers and administrators to efficiently manage and scale containerized workloads with ease.		
Gitlab link		Cluster Management available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/cluster_management		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first version in which Rancher on Kubernetes is installed and configured manually on Kubernetes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software pre-installation: Docker, K3s and Helm. • Installation of Rancher on Kubernetes cluster. 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the second version. It includes the integration of installing all software into a shell script, along with the necessary configuration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service verification and installation automation. • Modifying the Kubernetes node for SSL certificate configuration. • Adding a new cluster of AI-PRISM CMT for application deployment. 	Completed.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application catalogue in Rancher. • DNS deployment fixed with an alternative (cigip-dev branch). • Possibility to configure ssl certificates and secure access 	
3.0	April 2025	Final version of the script	Bug fixes and additional features identified during the integration	In progress

3.1.4. MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES

Module name		MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES		
General description		Machine learning templates for easy integration.		
Gitlab link		Cluster Management available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/ml-project-template		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	December 2023	This is the first version on templates	First generic ML template	In progress

3.1.5. ROS OVERLAY WORKSPACE HELM JOB TEMPLATE

Module name		ROS 2 OVERLAY WORKSPACE HELM JOB TEMPLATE		
General description		Helm template to install ROS 2 packages in a ROS 2 service running in an edge device using Helm jobs.		

Gitlab link		Project Template available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/job_install		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	September 2024	First version of ROS 2 overlay workspace template	Install ROS 2 packages in running ROS Framework service	Completed
2.0	April 2025	Final version	CI/CD stage to generate Helm charts automatically	In progress.

3.2. AI-BASED PERCEPTION ENHANCING MODULES – PE (FBK)

The GitLab software repository is available here: <https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules>.

3.2.1. OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION (2D/3D)

Module name		OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION		
General description		The “object and defect detection” module is designed to work in the VIGO pilot, among others. It detects objects and their positions, as well as defects in the semiconductor structure. Specifically, it consists of two components: the Defect Detection module, which enables the detection of defects on the chip using AI, and the Few-shot Key Point Detection module, which enables the detection of a selected chip fragment using AI.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here for Defect Detection : https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/object_and_defect_detection Gitlab is available here for Few-shot Key point Detection : https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/object_and_defect_detection/aiprism_deploy		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the first prototype of module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detects key points on the structure • Annotation tool implemented 	Completed
2.0	June-July 2024	This is the epic of the second version of the tool. Some improvements of existing features.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add CI/CD tools for containerisation 	Completed
3.0	April 2025	Third version. tooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add Helm-charts to catalogue via CI/CD • Add defects detection (postponed) 	In progress

3.2.2. OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION

Module name		OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION		
General description		This module performs model-based zero-shot object 6D pose estimation, determining the rotation and translation of an object within a scene. It takes as input the 3D point cloud representing the object and an RGBD image capturing a partial view of the scene and produces as output the object's rotation and translation transformations relative to the sensor's reference frame.		
Gitlab link		The Git repository is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/cluster_management . For now, the repository only contains a basic README file. We will release the code publicly by the end of the project.		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 31, 2024	First version of the code performing object 6D pose estimation without the need for task-specific training data	Python implementation based on the PyTorch library	Completed
2.0	June 2024	Second version of the code containing also a ROS2	Module demonstrator running in a controlled Lab	Completed

		wrapper of the python code released in v1 and a Gazebo simulator	environment containing a collaborative robotic arm spray painting a chair	
3.0	April 2025	Final version of the code.	Module demonstrator running in the Andreu World pilot facility	In progress

3.2.3. PCB GRASPING POINT ESTIMATION

Module name		PCB GRASPING POINT ESTIMATION		
General description		Detects PCB Boards and determines best grasping position. Detections and estimation are robust in different lighting conditions.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is not available yet/ Managed internally by the responsible partner.		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of März 2024	Initial iterations with various detection and grasping point estimation algorithms. Base design of training and execution pipeline.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluating different techniques empirically for detection and grasping point estimation. - Base version of training and execution pipeline. 	Completed
2.0	30 st of September 2024	Execution pipeline implementation done. Detection and grasping point estimation in different lighting conditions Implemented and verified through empirical testing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Object detection with Yolo8obb integrated - Successfully used a small data set (64 images) for transfer learning - Detections robust regardless of lighting conditions 	Completed

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grasping point estimation robust for densely packed PCBs - Grasping point estimation pipeline tested in laboratory environment 	
3.0	31st March 2025	Implementation on Edge device KEBA PLC. ROS2 Wrappers developed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Execution pipeline implemented on KEBA PLC. - Inference on edge device CPU (considering kernel-related limitations) 	Completed
4.0	31th of May 2025	Training on the Shopfloor pipeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training pipeline can be triggered by operator via UI - Automated training data acquisition - Introduction of Novel PCB types 	Planned

3.2.4. PCB POSE ESTIMATION

Module name	PCB POSE ESTIMATION			
General description	This module for PCB 6D-pose estimation—combining high-resolution 2D image registration with low-cost depth sensing—enables accurate and robust and precise PCB localization.			
Gitlab link	Gitlab is not available yet/ Managed internally by the responsible partner.			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	31st of March 2024	Initial Design of Ai-driven Image registration Pipeline.	- Ai-driven Image registration Pipeline.	Completed
2.0	30st of September 2024	Successfully implemented AI-driven image registration. Conducted experiments utilizing various feature extractors and matching techniques to evaluate performance.	- Implemented Pose Estimation Pipeline -Conducted various Experiments for evaluation	Completed
3.0	31st of March 2025	Integrated a two-stage approach to achieve both high accuracy and low latency.	- two-stage approach -high accuracy and low latency	Completed
4.0	31st of May 2025	ROS2 Wrappers		Planned
5.0	30th of September 2025	TBD	TBD	TBD

3.2.5. 2D DEFECT DETECTION

Module name	2D DEFECT DETECTION			
General description	The 2D Defect detection module is designed to detect, analyze, and classify objects, defects, or patterns using advanced computer vision and AI techniques. This component has been specifically designed to provide improved accuracy, efficiency, and robustness in industrial settings and is deployed in SILVERLINE pilot			
Gitlab link	The link to the repository: 2D Defect Detection			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	June 2024	The initial release of the defect detection module with basic AI-based analysis and detection capabilities.	AI-based object detection, image analysis for defects	Completed
2.0	August 2024	The updated version with enhanced defect classification and more robust performance in industrial environments.	Improved accuracy, additional defect categories, enhanced processing speed	Completed
3.0	January 2025	Optimizing the system for real-time processing at scale and ensuring its seamless deployment	Real-time functionality	Completed

3.2.6. SPEECH RECOGNITION

Module name	Speech Recognition			
General description	The Speech Recognition module is designed to recognize speech as part of seamless human-machine interaction.			
Gitlab link	The Git repository is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/speech-recognition			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Jan 2024	Demo with controlled audio recording of voice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transcribe audio recording to text 	Completed

2.0	Feb 2025	Demo automatic recognition.	with live	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automatic voice activity detection Keyword detection 	Completed
3.0	TBD	Fixes improvements.	and		In progress

3.2.7. NLP INTENT AND SLOT

Module name		NLP INTENT AND SLOT			
General description		This component allows interpreting user commands from text (output from speech recognition) as part of human-machine interaction.			
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/nlp-intent-and-slot			
Released versions					
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status	
1.0	Jan 2024	Demo utterances recognized into basic commands.	with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NLP model architecture based on BERT 	Completed
2.0	Feb 2025	Demo utterances recognized into pilot-specific commands.	with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved model training Command set for KEBA pilot 	Completed
3.0	TBD	Fixes improvements.	and		In progress

3.2.8. PERSON FOLLOWER

Module name		PERSON FOLLOWER			
General description		This component allows to detect and track a person in the collaboration ambient using the 3d camera equipped in AGVs, for the purpose of following them around.			

Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/person-follower		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Sep 2024	Minimal demo with recorded video.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detect and track person • Display data for following person 	Completed
2.0	Dec 2024	ROS interface for integration with other modules.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate using pilot-wide ROS interface 	Completed
3.0	Mar 2025	Acceleration of detection and tracking with Hailo AI.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase performance with Hailo 	In progress
4.0	TBD	Rancher deployment, other fixes and improvements.		

3.2.9. HOOD DETECTION AND TRACKING

Module name				
General description		This AI-driven perception component is designed to detect and track hood components in real time. Using machine vision and deep learning algorithms, it processes camera feeds to identify hood positions and movements, enabling robots to interact dynamically with detected objects.		
Gitlab link		The link to the repository: Hood Detection and Tracking		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 2024	Initial release of the object detection module with basic tracking and position detection.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-based object tracking and processing by using video records. 	Completed
2.0	September 2024	Version with added support for multi-hood detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic tracking of hood components, 	Completed

		and tracking, handling multiple components simultaneously.	enhanced AI capabilities, improved system scalability.	
3.0	May 2025	Enhanced version with improved object tracking accuracy	Calibration for real-time environment	In progress

3.2.10. FOLLOW ME AMR MODULE-UWB

Module name		FOLLOW ME AMR MODULE-UWB		
General description		The Follow me AMR module - UWB module detects and tracks a person in the collaborative environment using Ultra Wide Band sensor data. This technology allows collaborative robots to track a person even if there is no line of sight.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/uwb		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 31 st , 2025	ROS2 node used to receive data from the UWB server and a launch file implementing this node with Nav2 to follow the target tag. It creates a UDP socket and publishes the filtered information received from the server.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 driver for the UWB- AMR follow-me application available in repository. 	Completed

3.2.11. Inference Component: AI-Engine

Module name		INFERENCE COMPONENT: AI-ENGINE		
General description		Computer Vision model to detect persons, forklift and dangerous areas (through geo-fencing).		
Gitlab link				

Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	End of project	Computer vision model trained with public data and optimized for edge deployment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Object detection • Worker detection • Virtual geo-fencing 	In progress

3.2.12. AFFECTIVE WORKER CONDITION MONITORING

Module name		AFFECTIVE WORKER CONDITION MONITORING (FORMER HEALTH STATUS MONITORING)		
General description		Components that use biometric data and context information (ocular activity, cardiovascular activity, cognitive load, task execution) to detect psychophysiological states influencing workers' conditions.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/reference-architecture/-/tree/dev-upv/docs/guides/Components/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/affective_worker_condition_monitoring		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	30th April 2025	First release of structured biometric data (fixations, saccades, blinks, heart rate, R-R interval)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First release of biometric anonymised data 	In progress
2.0	End of Project	Final release of Affective Worker Condition Monitoring module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final release of the AI module calculating workers' psychophysiological states 	-

3.2.13. HUMAN STATUS ESTIMATION

Module name				
General description		This module assesses human posture and determines the worker's status by detecting abnormal behaviours. The module first receives video input of a worker collaborating with a cooperative robot. It then estimates the worker's posture from the input video and assesses the		

		musculoskeletal risk level. Finally, it segments the entire work process into individual tasks, identifying frequent and abnormal patterns in task execution.		
Gitlab link		Due to company and government security regulations, code sharing via GitLab is currently under internal discussion.		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	10th March 2025	First release of Manufacturing Worker Status Estimation module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human pose estimation from collaborative work video input Collaborative work posture risk assessment 	Done
2.0	End of Project	Final release of Manufacturing Worker Status Estimation module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration task segmentation from video input Frequent and anomaly pattern detection in human pose 	In progress

3.2.14. HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION

Module name				
General description		This AI-based module can be used to recognise human activity from video.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/human-activity-recognition		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Oct 2023	Minimal demo showing recognition of PCB handling activity of operator at KEBA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on video with annotated time segments 	
2.0	End of Project	Final release		

3.3. AI-BASED AGENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – DR (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/agent-level-reasoning-acting-and-control>

3.3.1. COORDINATION OF AGENTS

Module name		BetFSM		
General description		This module will coordinate the different agents that play a role in the execution of tasks (e.g. control, vision, planning, etc).		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repository: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/projects/ai-prism/ai-prism-controller . Partial code is released in AI-PRISM the under group: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/agent-level-reasoning-acting-and-control		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	A finite state machine that coordinates the application. For the insertion of the PCB, it checks for the insertion states before executing the next phase so that the insertion becomes robust (e.g. first make contact with the corner, then one of the sides, etc).	Completed
2.0	30 st of September 2024	Integration of Yasmin state machines with ROS2 eTaSL (cf. Section 3.6)	State machines for specifying the discrete state aspects of robotic skills	Completed
2.1	30 st of September 2024	Interfacing of state machines with higher level orchestration	A ROS2 action interface has been developed for Yasmin state machines	Completed

2.2	30st of September 2024	Orchestration of application	Behaviortree.CPP action node that interfaces with the action implemented in v2.1	Completed
3.0	25th of February 2025	BetFSM module for coordination with Finite State Machines that use Behavior Tree primitives was developed because of the identified shortcomings of Yasmin. The module is not dependent anymore of Yasmin at all.	-Python3 API - ROS2 integration for using services, topics, lifecycle state machines, etc - Action server to execute FSMs - Possibility to declare FSMs with a mix between traditional primitives and Behaviour trees primitives (e.g. sequence, concurrent, fallback, etc)	Completed
3.1	30th April 2025	Skill formalization using BetFSM	- Create re-usable skills using BetFSM and etasl - Mechanisms to create libraries of skills that can be installed and easily used thanks to JSON Schemas	In progress

3.3.2. BT ORCHESTRATOR

Module name		BT ORCHESTRATOR		
General description		A Behavior Tree-driven orchestrator that manages teaching, Ai-driven execution, and deviation handling workflows.		
Gitlab link		Available in private Git repositories for the moment		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	30st of September 2024	The concept of a BT orchestrator and executor for all scenarios was developed, and initial behavior trees were tested in the	- Data sharing between High Level Orchestrator blackboard and the Task executor blackboard	Completed

		laboratory environment.	- Robotic tasks for manipulating the laboratory Robot	
2.0	31st March 2025	This module provides a BT-based control framework for the Keba PCB testing cell. It integrates robotic tasks (detection, pickup, placement) with a vision-based PCB detection system. The BT orchestrator complies with the JSON schema defined by PROF and KUL.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full set of BTs for Keba PCB testing cell. - Integrated vision system (PCB detection) with BT orchestrator - JSON schema compliance (PROF/KUL standard) - Successfully passed integration tests (vision and control) 	In Progress
3.0	31th of May 2025	This iteration extends the BT orchestrator by integrating KUL modules and additional vision modules, such as the PCB re-orientation system. It also adds behavior trees for system re-configuration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BT orchestrator integration with KUL and additional vision and control modules - Behavior trees for system re-configuration for novel PCB type 	Planned

3.3.3. FORCE-BASED BEHAVIOURS

Module name		FORCE-BASED BEHAVIOURS		
General description		Module that provides force-based behaviours for compliant execution.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here:		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	31 st of June 2024	Re-usable set of constraints that can be used to create tasks that require force control (e.g. hand guiding or insertions).	- Admittance constraints to create different task specifications	Completed
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3.3.4. DEPLOYABLE CONSTRAINT BASED REACTIVE CONTROL

Module name		DEPLOYABLE CONSTRAINT BASED REACTIVE CONTROL		
General description		Deployable reactive controller to execute constraint-based and sensor-based tasks programmed in eTaSL language. Some tasks can be purely modeled and some others can be learned through the PbD toolkit.		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repository: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob-expressiongraphs/ros2/etasl_ros2		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case based on Orocos (no ROS2)	Executes learned skills for certain parts of the task (e.g. pick the pcb), and modeled skills for others (e.g. robust force-based insertion)	Completed
2.0	1 st of September 2024	Development of a ROS2 node that is independent of Orocos and can be used to execute eTaSL skills.	A highly configurable ROS2 node for task specification and execution ready.	Completed
2.1	15 th of January	Increase usability by making the node easily reconfigurable through the use of JSON schemas	-Can reconfigure properties with Autocompletion and self-contained documentation thanks to JSON Schemas	Completed

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generic way to interface with robots via shared memory. Kuka iiwa integrated - Partial Documentation using MK Docs integrated in Gitlab pages with CI/CD. 	
2.2	5 th of March	Organized template and mechanisms to create libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -An application template facilitates integration of new applications - Task specification libraries can now be easily installed and reused. - JSON Schemas describing parameters of task specifications are automatically generated from the task specification file when building the application template package with colcon. 	Ready to be tested
2.3	TBD	Augmenting usability, adding features, and completing tutorials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adding features such as new input/output handlers for other relevant msg topic types - More testing - Complete tutorials 	In progress

3.4. AI-BASED AMBIENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – CR (UPV)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning>

3.4.1. REASONING MODEL

Module name		REASONING MODEL		
General description		Collaboration Ambient Data Model The Collaboration ambient data model is a data model that adds context to the data collected in the Data Platform. Based on control and enterprise systems integration standards, the model defines the production specifications (operations, materials, personnel, or equipment requirements), capacities, production scheduling and production performance information.		
Gitlab link		AI-PRISM data model available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning/aiprism-reasoning-model		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	January 21 st 2024	This is the first version of the data model. It defines the main model structure and documentation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation about the Data Model. • Definition Model tables. • Capability Model tables. • Schedule Model tables. 	Completed
2.0	March 2024	This second version includes a first instance of the model based on AW use case.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition inserts • Schedule inserts 	Completed
3.0	September 2024	The third version provides the possibility of importing data from an Excel files.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Node-Red flow to import and structure data. • Several performance improvements 	Completed
3.1	February-March 2025	The third version of the data model went under refinements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated Data for Equipment Model, Personnel Model 	Ready to test

		to effectively store additional data	Operations definition and operations segment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testing of the scheduling algorithm 	
4.0	April 2025 -May	Final release	New features and bug fixes found during the integration	In progress

3.4.2. HRC PAINTING RE/SCHEDULER

Module name		HRC PAINTING RE/SCHEDULER		
General description		The AI-PRISM Scheduling model is a representation of all entities, their properties and the relation between them. This model allows the scheduling of the factory processes taking into consideration all available resources and restrictions, including cobots and its training requirements.		
Gitlab link		Available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning/aw-scheduler		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	November 31 st 2023	Gather data necessity and data output from initial design and generate an initial data model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial data model for scheduling module input • Initial data model for scheduling module output 	Completed
2.0	March 2024	Generate a second iteration for data model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated data model 	In progress
3.0	End of March 2024	Create a standardized version of the data model according to standard IEC62264	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized data model 	In progress
3.0	March 2024	Service API for scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dockerized scheduling service API 	Ready to test
4.0	April 2025	Scheduling API tests with live data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test API • Check results 	In progress

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update scheduling service (if necessary) 	
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3.5. HUMAN - MACHINE INTERACTION (HMI) MODULES – HI (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction>

3.5.1. KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE

Module name		KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE		
General description		The module allows the users to interact with the robot by force interaction in cartesian space by an admittance controlled based on measured forces in the end effector. The module can be re-configured to allow changes in position, orientation, or both.		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repository: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/projects/ai-prism/ai-prism-controller A project with a basic readme has already been added to AI-PRISM git repository: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/kinesthetic-teaching-interface		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	The module allows the user to kinaesthetically guide the robot, without relying on the kinaesthetic functionalities provided by the robot manufacturer	Ready to test
1.1	1 st of June 2024	Demonstration of kinaesthetic teaching interface in use case inspired by KEBA pilot case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Force-based physical human interaction - Informed by the learning from demonstration to allow only variations that occur during 	Demonstrated into pilot-inspired use case

			demonstration phase	
2.0	TBD	Backend integration to facilitate user re-configuration and execution	Facilitates mode switching	Integration in ROS2 is ongoing
3.0	TBD	Frontend integration to facilitate user re-configuration and execution	Allows the user to launch the kinaesthetic interaction from a GUI	Planned

3.5.2. HRC ASSEMBLY CONSTRAINT-BASED TASKS

Module name		HRC ASSEMBLY CONSTRAINT-BASED TASKS		
General description		This module provides task specifications involving HRC in assembly		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repository		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Task specifications with hardcoded parameters to perform assembly operations with HRC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tasks (e.g. approach, make contact, etc) related to assembly applications. • Hardcoded parameters that makes it hard to re-use • Implementation done in Orocos (not ROS2) 	Completed
2.0	1 st of September 2024	Task specifications with hardcoded parameters to perform assembly operations with HRC running in ROS2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same task specifications as before but now running in ROS2 	Completed

3.0	15 th April 2025	Re-usable task specifications with automatically generated JSON Schemas for parameters, organized in task specification libraries	-Task specifications now are reusable and can be configured -They are organized in installable task specification libraries	In progress

3.5.3. SPEECH SYNTHESIS

Module name	SPEECH SYNTHESIS			
General description	This module synthesizes the robot voice for feedback as part of the voice control HMI.			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/speech-synthesis			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Feb 2025	Demo with voice feedback as part of voice control.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synthesize voice audio from text 	Completed
2.0	TBD	Fixes and improvements.		In progress

3.5.4. VOICE CONTROL

Module name	VOICE CONTROL			
General description	This module provides a Natural Language HMI interface to control the robot, by orchestrating the data flow from related sub-modules and implementing a natural dialog flow.			
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/voice-control			

Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Feb 2025	Demo of basic voice control with voice feedback.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orchestration of voice and NLP related submodules • Basic dialog flow 	Completed
2.0	May 2025	ROS interface for integration with other modules.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate using pilot-wide ROS interface 	In progress
3.0	TBD	Rancher deployment, other fixes and improvements.	TBD	In progress

3.5.5. SMART PICK AND PLACE FOR RECYCLING

Module name		SMART PICK AND PLACE FOR RECYCLING		
General description		This AI-powered module uses advanced detection and segmentation with a stereo camera to locate bottles on a moving conveyor. A collaborative robot arm then picks and sorts the bottles, minimizing waste and improving efficiency.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	13st of February 2024	Sensor data are used to create collision models of multiple bottles to enhance performance in dynamic environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obstacle detection. • Collision models creation. 	Completed
1.1	15th of April 2024	Fine tune Open Motion Planning Library solver and add Pilz.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMPL configuration updated. • PILZ included. 	Completed
2.0	TBD	AI detection and segmentation model of bottles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial bottle detection. • Include multiple types of bottles. 	In progress

3.5.6. COLLABORATIVE ORDER FORMING

Module name		COLLABORATIVE ORDER FORMING		
General description		This AI-powered module enables an Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) to detect, track, and follow a designated person using LIDAR data. It maintains a safe distance, avoids obstacles, and enhances warehouse picking efficiency by seamlessly assisting workers.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of February 2024	Simple human following algorithm via leg detection and pairing without tracking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leg detection via Random Forest on laser data. • Simple geometric leg pairing. • Simple human following for omnidirectional AMR. 	Completed
1.1	31 st of May 2024	Simple human following algorithm via leg detection and pairing with Kalman tracking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upgraded leg detection with map masking: Significant reduction of false positives. • Advanced leg pairing using global nearest neighbours and multi-person tracking via Kalman filtering. • Simple following of locked target for any AMR 	Completed
1.2	31 st of January 2025	Robust and safe human following algorithm via leg detection and pairing with Kalman tracking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust following while respecting costmap obstacles. • Safe distance form operator. • State machine and interactivity with the operator. 	Completed

3.5.7. SMART DEPALLETIZING

Module name		SMART DEPALLETIZING		
General description		This AI-driven module utilizes advanced detection and segmentation to dynamically locate powder sacks on loaded pallets, providing precise coordinates for a robotic suction system to efficiently pick and handle them.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	13st of February 2024	Sensor data are used to create collision models of sacks to enhance performance in dynamic environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obstacle detection. • Collision models creation. 	Completed
1.1	15th of April 2024	Fine tune Open Motion Planning Library solver and add Pilz.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMPL configuration updated. • PILZ included. 	Completed
2.0	TBD	AI detection and segmentation model of sacks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial sack detection. • Include multiple types of sacks. 	In progress

3.5.8. AI ASSISTANT

Module name		AI ASSISTANT		
General description		This AI Assistant helps unskilled people operate robots with ease.		
Gitlab link		Not available		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	31 st of June 2025	By providing clear, step-by-step instructions, it simplifies complex tasks and ensures safe, efficient operation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The assistant includes multilingual capabilities to enhance accessibility and helps operators to solve problems at the machine. 	In progress
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3.6. PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT – PD (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction>

3.6.1. PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION TOOLKIT

Module name		PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION TOOLKIT		
General description		Toolkit to analyse demonstrations data and generate a learned motion model		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repositories: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/projects/ai-prism/ai-prism-controller and https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/phd/cristian-vergara/u0108073/traPPCA_lib		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	- Acquires demonstrations of some parts of the task and generated a learned model in a JSON format.	Completed
1.1	31 st of sept 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	Specific skills to demonstrate the picking and placing of PCB's	Completed
2.0	15 th of May 2025	Preliminary toolkit version for processing demonstrations	-Python implementation to process set of demonstrations	In progress

			- Configurable parameters to adapt to learning situation	
2.1	15 th of July 2025	Toolkit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Backend implementation to easily record and process demonstrations - Visualization tools to help to analyze the generated motion model - Kinematic simulation facilities to test with a virtual robot 	Planned

3.6.2. PAINTING PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION

Module name		PAINTING PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION		
General description		The module allows the users to interact with the robot in a virtual reality environment. It allows to control the painting robot remotely or to teach how to paint new pieces of furniture.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/programming-by-demonstration-with-vr		
Released versions		2		
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Preliminary demonstrator for internal review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Control the robot in virtual reality - Control a UR robot using TCP sockets 	Completed
2.0	December 2024	ROS 2 compatibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with ROS 2 driver - Integration with other WP4 components (reasoning model and cluster management) 	In progress
3.0	TBD	Final version	New features and bug fixes identified during tests	Planned

3.6.3. MULTIMODAL INTERFACES

Module name		MULTIMODAL INTERFACES		
General description		This module on multi-modal interfaces—integrates GUI, kinesthetic, and vision-based interactions—enhances robot task programming by enabling intuitive, adaptive, and user-friendly interaction, facilitating seamless human-robot collaboration in dynamic industrial environments.		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repositories.		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31st of March 2024	This module Utilizes hand-guiding mode for human-driven configuration the PCB picking task. Key processes include template creation, transformation calculations, and related tasks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prototype-level development - PCB picking configuration utilizing Kinesthetic Teaching - Configuration Template generation - Transformation and alignment calculations 	Completed
2.0	30st of September 2024	Vision-based system for teaching and correcting PCB pose prior to placement. The system is utilized after the human-assisted PCB picking configuration step. It uses sensor fusion combining low-cost and industrial-grade imaging solutions. The process includes PCB alignment into the focus plane of the camera.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vision-based PCB pose teaching - Sensor fusion (low-cost + industrial cameras) - PCB alignment into focus plane 	Completed
3.0	31st of March 2025	Simple User Interface for grasping point teaching, enhanced with AI that suggests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intuitive grasp point teaching utilizing GUI - AI-based grasp point suggestion 	Completed

		efficient grasping points for novel PCB Types, with algorithms that consider end-effector geometries.	- Algorithms account for specific end-effector geometries	
4.0	31st of May 2025	An intuitive react GUI serves the operator with various teaching modalities, allowing individual selection based on individual preferences. Additionally, a configuration wizard enables workers on the shopfloor to create new PCB configurations directly.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intuitive GUI for operator interaction - Multiple selectable teaching modalities - Configuration wizard for creating new PCB configurations for novel PCB types. - Target Operator: non robotic expert. 	Planned
5.0	30th of September 2025	TBD	TBD	TBD

3.6.4. SKILLS FOR COMPLEX TASKS

Module name		SKILLS FOR COMPLEX TASKS		
General description		Skills for complex tasks that require force-based robot behaviors (e.g. insertion) or learning from demonstrations		
Gitlab link				
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

<p>1.0</p>	<p>31st of March 2024</p>	<p>Examples of skills for complex tasks such as insertions in Orocos</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented through a collection of task specifications and coordination with rFSM in Orocos. • Hardcoded parameters which make the skill difficult to reuse 	<p>Completed</p>
<p>2.0</p>	<p>31st of sept 2024</p>	<p>Examples of skills for complex tasks such as insertions in ROS2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented through a collection of task specifications and coordination with Yasmin in ROS2. • Hardcoded parameters which make the skill difficult to reuse 	<p>Completed</p>
<p>3.0</p>	<p>15th of May 2025</p>	<p>Re-usable skill libraries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented through tasks coming from task specification libraries and coordination with BetFSM in ROS2. • Reconfigurable through parameters with JSON Schemas • Organized in re-usable skill libraries 	<p>In Progress</p>

4. Conclusions

4.1.1. SUMMARY

The report describes the software versions and their status in a tabular manner, containing high-level information of the consecutive releases of the CI/CD framework and AI-based enhancing modules designed to enhance the perception and reasoning capabilities of robotic agents within the collaborative environment. The document contains the details and status of the components developed from months 7 to 30. The high-level description of each module

describes its purpose in the project and project pilot, links to software and documentation, and the status and features of its consecutive released versions. Together, this deliverable and its companion D3.3. document the status of all software components developed in AI-PRISM.

4.1.2. **NEXT STEPS**

The next versions of deliverable will contain descriptions of subsequent versions of the software including the versions in project in the current document as well as versions that have not been planned or started yet.